

Public Leadership Behavior of Supervisors and Professional Commitment of Employees: The Mediating Role of Work Engagement of Employees of the Local Government Unit

Derbert B. General¹, Lorna T. General²

University of Mindanao Davao City Professional Schools

Abstract:- This study aimed to reveal the public leadership behavior of supervisors and professional commitment of employees: mediating role of work engagement of employees of local government unit. Utilizing the non-experimental quantitative research design employing correlation technique of research and mediation analysis for an in-depth analysis of the study, the researcher utilized adapted questionnaires to three hundred ten employees of local government unit of province of Davao Oriental, Philippines, in the school year 2022-2023. Mean, Pearson r and Path Analysis were the statistical tools used. The results revealed that public leadership behavior of supervisors had a very high extent in all indicators and the professional commitment had high mean level. Whereas, the work engagement had a high mean rating. Furthermore, findings revealed that public leadership behavior and work engagement showed significant relationships, work engagement and professional commitment and public leadership behavior and professional commitment.

Utilizing the path analysis, the results of the study revealed partial mediating effect of work engagement on the relationship between public leadership behavior and professional commitment. This implies that the mediating role played by work engagement of government employees partially assisted in clarifying the process that was responsible for the relationship between public leadership behavior and professional commitment.

Keywords:- Public administration, work engagement, public leadership behavior and professional commitment., Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, employee professional commitment is considered insufficient. Sena (2020) states that 90% of employees lack a strong commitment to their organization. The cause of this shortfall is employees' dissatisfaction with their organization, which also leads to employees' lack of motivation to complete the task. At the same time, Arthi and Sumathi (2020) found that employees who lack motivation and job satisfaction also lack commitment to their organizations.

By this logic, it must be assumed that the degree of commitment can be expressed by the intensity phase of the motivation. It determines the amount of energy used to achieve the goal (Aboramadan, & Dahleez, 2020). Therefore, commitment has attribution meaning, as it distinguishes actions motivated by the belief about the need to perform and perform them with great effort to achieve the goal that accompanies the committed action. , i.e. get the best end result. Naturally, organizations value having engaged employees in their ranks because their work is effective (Park, Han, Kim, & Kim, 2022).

Incidentally, in an age of fierce competition in any business or organization, employee professional commitment should be a tagline. Much attention has been paid to research on organizational commitment by researchers and scholars (Duran, Celik, Ertugrul, Ok & Albayrak, 2021); Margaretha, Saragih, Zaniarti and Parayow, 2021); Permatasari, Purwana and Akbar, 2020); Obuobisa-Darko, 2021) with the hope of identifying the dynamics of professional engagement so that organizations can survive tough competitions taking place in both local, national or global contexts (Wang, Xu, Zhang and Li, 2020); Tian and Zhang, 2020), but the issue of professional engagement continues to be a burning issue in both the private and public sectors. This indicates a gap somewhere along the line.

In today's highly competitive world, the commitment of professionals to their organization makes sense as a credo, especially when higher productivity is required. But that doesn't happen in government-run businesses, agencies or organizations. What is noticeable in these organizations, however, is the decline in productivity (Norouzinik, Rahimnia, Maharati, & Eslami, 2022), possibly due to employees' lack of commitment to the vision, mission, and goals. organization's. (Luu, 2019; Meynhardt, Brieger and Hermann, 2020; Aggarwal, Chand, Jhamb and Mittal, 2020; Xu, Li and Wang, 2021).

Furthermore, according to Manalo, de Castro and Uy (2020), career commitment increases productivity, regular attendance, and increased intention to stay in the organization. Furthermore, to date, there has been extensive research on public leadership (Vogel & Werkmeister, 2021; Sorensen, Bryson, & Crosby, 2021) since its introduction two decades ago (Bateman & Organ, 1983). Public leadership scholars have long considered managerial leadership to be an important factor in the effective

functioning of government organizations, including the delivery of better and effective services. Commitment represents a willingness to put in great effort to achieve the best results for the organization and the people it leads. This type of leadership can motivate subordinates to perform at their best and support the core ideas of the team. If team members see their leaders invested in the business, it motivates them to stay in the organization and work hard for its growth (Gamboa, Ilac, Carangan) & Agida, 2021).

The aim of this study was to examine the mediating effect of job engagement on the relationship between supervisor's public leadership behavior and job engagement. More specifically, the study will seek to answer the following questions. The first objective is to assess the extent of public leadership by supervisors in terms of accountability, legitimacy, ethics, and political loyalty; and network administrator. Assess the level of professional commitment in terms of emotional career commitment, continuing career commitment; and standard professional commitment. Furthermore, the fourth describes the level of commitment to work in terms of strong, dedicated; and absorption. Identify a meaningful relationship between a supervisor's public leadership behavior and professional commitment; mass leadership behavior and commitment to work and commitment to work and commitment to work. To determine whether the mediating effect of job engagement on the relationship between supervisors' public leadership behavior and job engagement.

The following null hypotheses were treated at the 0.05 significance level. public leadership behavior and work commitment and work commitment and career commitment. To determine whether the mediating effect of job engagement on the relationship between supervisors' public leadership behavior and job engagement.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This section provides discussion of the principles, concepts, ideas and perspectives of various authors, who have provided valuable contributions on Directions include: responsibility, legitimacy, ethics, political loyalty; and network administration (Murray, 1983). Likewise, discussions were also provided on teacher engagement, which emphasized vitality, dedication and receptivity (Balducci, Fraccaroli, & Schaufeli, 2010). Career commitment focuses on emotional career commitment (APC), continuing career commitment (CPC), and normative career commitment (Meyer, Allen & Smith, 1993).

There is no daily active interaction with their employees, nor the human side their job, other aspects of the leader's responsibilities will be affected. Leadership is a two-way commitment between leaders and employees to achieve a common goal. This commitment motivates leaders to influence employee behavior while also influencing employee perception. This leads to expectations of appropriate behavior rooted in the organizational environment (Vogel, Reuber, & Vogel, 2020).

In addition, in many cases, leaders who are successful in inspiring and motivating others have high levels of energy and enthusiasm. They energize their team to achieve difficult goals and enhance the performance of all team members. Many leaders focus only on completing the task in the job description and forget about inspiring (Mitra, 2020).

In any organization, leaders are often responsible for failure. Because of this, your employees may be threatened to take the next step and grow in their role for fear of taking on new responsibilities. To change this behavior and create an environment where all levels can thrive and work as a team, see failure as a learning opportunity and make it a fundamental tenet of your culture. , rather than an opportunity to blame (Wexler & Oberlander, 2020).

Likewise, based on a survey of public and private sector managers who Accountability is considered the most important value for the public sector. Much significant scholarly work has been devoted to accountability, including leadership and accountability. However, responsibility is an elusive concept. It is an evocative political word and is often used as a symbol of good governance. Therefore, it is necessary to clearly define the concept. He notes that the most concise description of responsibility would be the obligation to explain and justify such behavior (Schwarz, Eva & Newman, 2020).

Employee engagement and loyalty are very important to the organization, as Monje-Amor, Vázquez and Faña (2020) pointed out about positive relationships with the organization, in which employees are instrumental help the organization achieve its goals or succeed. Decuyper and Schaufeli (2020) also do not observe that individuals who are committed to an organization have positive feelings towards the organization, demonstrate a desire to stay in the organization, have a strong confidence and perception of values and goals of the organization and is willing to do the best work for the organization. Because engaged employees possess energetic and emotional connections to their work activities, see themselves as capable of meeting the demands of the job and delivering on their commitment. them to others in the workplace (Bakker, 2009; Demerouti et al., 2010), so they are more likely to contribute to the sustainable development of individuals and organizations while promoting a place healthy work (Bakker et al., 2011). It is important for organizations to get a feel for the true nature of engagement, especially in the public sector, to better define its drivers (Mostafa & AbedEl-Motalib, 2020).

Engaged employees exhibit high energy and mental resilience, and they tend to be willing to invest significant effort in assigned tasks. In addition, highly engaged employees tend to be aware of the importance and challenges of their work, and show enthusiasm and pride in their work, thereby improving their performance. their capacity. Although the concept of commitment is pervasive and the amount of research in the field of engagement is increasing (Demerouti et al., 2010), this topic has not received adequate research attention in recent years. recently. ., 2019).

While the focus is on identifying and nurturing the positive effects of job engagement, developing programs for those who are not fully engaged (or not actively engaged) can also same priority. In particular, disengaged individuals reported an inability to cope effectively with the political environment, largely due to a lack of personal and professional resources (Kane-Frieder et al. 2014).

Studies have shown that emotional attachment to the company can develop and mature into a strong commitment to the organization from employees who report they are satisfied with the organization. For example, in a study conducted by Supardi, Yulianah and Ariawan (2023), it was found that 40% of employees who are very satisfied with their organization are likely to develop a strong emotional commitment to the organization. their. In contrast, the remaining percentage of employees is unlikely to grow in this way. In addition, in a study conducted by Salim, Buhari, Yong and Lee (2020), they found that increasing engagement at work, perceived organizational support and satisfaction at work is an effective way to attract highly engaged employees, which implies that if organizations require commitment from their employees, they must first take the first step towards satisfaction. its staff. Influential organizational commitment also benefits employees. Employees with a high degree of emotional commitment experience lower levels of stress even though they work longer and harder than those without engagement. Emotional attachment encourages motivation and reduces work-related physical and psychological stress, is less emotionally draining, and personalized (Meriç, & Erdem, 2020).

Employees who are engaged with their organizations, jobs, and careers seem happier and are able to spend more quality time with their families and hobbies. Individual employee involvement and commitment to work groups improves team performance, pro-social behavior, and team cohesion, which in turn improves performance and job satisfaction. People who are engaged in their work and/or career have less absenteeism and less intention to quit, increasing job satisfaction and increasing intrinsic motivation (Sunyoto, 2020).

The Side Betting Theory, according to Becker (1960), holds that there are certain investments made by employees in an organization that make it more difficult for them to leave the organization because of the effort to leave the organization, the investment of "side bets". " be done. in the organization will be lost. Thus, the theory is that employees develop high levels of commitment when they perceive that they have invested time, effort, and other personal resources in an organization that would be lost if they terminated their status. members of the organization and could not find another job.

apply their abilities and resources to a given cause. This ability is necessary to discussions about charismatic or transformational leadership in general and in education sector in particular. It sheds light on how individuals influence others and persuade them to devote all their efforts to tasks that help them achieve their goals. However, few studies have directly examined the relationship between

different styles Leadership and different types of motivation among followers (Bono and Judge, 2003)

This theory is based on the prepositions of Ying and Zaman (2008) that leadership behaviors affect commitment. Leadership behavior is more selective about employee performance. This means that the better the leadership behavior, the higher the professional commitment and the more incentive to create a favorable working atmosphere in the organization. With good leadership style, it will create trust that superiors care about not only in the organization/working unit but also in other working units.

When leaders understand the pillars of engagement, then they can begin to leverage employee engagement to achieve positive organizational outcomes such as better employee retention, satisfaction, and more. higher customer satisfaction and better financial performance. There are efforts to increase employee engagement by improving leadership (Aggarwal, Chand, Jhamb, & Mittal, 2020).

Additionally, employees who stay engaged and committed to their organizations give businesses important competitive advantages, including increased productivity and reduced employee turnover. It is therefore not surprising that organizations of all sizes and types have made substantial investments in policies and practices that promote the cohesion and cohesion of their workforces (Ahakwa, Yang, Tackie & Atingabili, 2021).

Furthermore, leadership behavior affects organizational commitment and employee performance because they are responsible for leading their employees to achieve their work goals. Therefore, leadership behavior is one of the important factors affecting organizational commitment (Yiing & Zaman, 2009). Additionally, public leadership behavior that fosters employee engagement and provides a clear vision can help employees internalize organizational goals and understand how valuable their contributions are. How to achieve that vision (Schwarz, 2017)

As for negative leadership behaviors, studies have shown that abusive leadership is inversely associated with emotional commitment and persistence (Rayner & Keashly, 2005). In turn, Mehta and Maheshwari (2013) suggest that there is an inverse relationship between perceived toxic leadership behaviors and organizational commitment. This finding supports the results of Weaver and Yancy (2010) that negative leadership is inversely related to employees' emotional commitment and positively related to their intention to leave the organization.

If overt leadership behavior is not aligned with an employee's career goals, it can cause employees to become more committed to their cause than to the organization, which will have the opposite effect on employee performance. organization (Cohen, 2003). Organizations where employees can commit to the organization, but not on an individual level (i.e. employees lead to status quo performance or performance below expectations (Cohen, 2013).

Leadership can influence employee behavior in an organization in relation to attitudes, motivation, and performance, all of which can affect engagement levels. In this sense, leaders, when interacting with their teams, use a combination of characteristics, skills, and behaviors related to leadership styles. These are often based on a combination of their beliefs, ideas, norms and values (Iqbal, Inayat, Ijaz & Zahid, 2012). Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study. The independent variables are public leadership behaviors that focus on accountability referring to accountability, the legitimacy of being authorized or recognized by law; legitimacy, oral ethics, principles that govern one's behavior or conduct an activity, political loyalty, dedication, and network governance refer to the regime most commonly associated with management concept. The dependent variable on career commitment has the following indicators (Meyer et al., 1993), namely: emotional commitment or so-called emotional attachment, identification and participation in the organization; Ongoing commitment refers to the perceived costs associated with leaving the organization, and; Normative commitment is known as perceived obligation to stay in the organization. While the intermediate variable is job engagement with the following indicators; vitality, enthusiasm or intensity; devotion or the state of absorption of devotion, or the process of absorption or the state of being (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2003).

This study is important from the point of view of government employees in different countries, as it will serve as a basis for system adoption and improvement. Good leadership is needed to establish the voice for an effective, efficient and ethical government. Good leaders instill confidence in government and its ability to serve its people, while ensuring that government policies meet the needs of the people (Spicer, 2016).

Furthermore, the findings of this study could be a first step in developing a leadership framework in this area by identifying leaders' leadership activities. Identifying the ways in which their leaders practice leadership consistently will lead to an early understanding of the type of leadership that exists in Davao Oriental. Employee involvement can provide an opportunity to tailor leadership training to meet needs and help them develop better leadership with autonomy. Participating in this research can help leaders use the results as a reflective tool to gauge their leadership confidence and performance, while providing key leaders with insight into the future. points and experiences to observe the benefits of using assessment tools as a guide for learning, development, and problem-solving. solve. From themselves, leaders can model the use of assessment tools and implement its use in the growth of their organizations and so that employees can work according to the codes of practice. work has been established and requires close supervision of employees so that employees can perform better in the future.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Participants

Respondents in this study included only regular employees of Mati City Hall and Capital Provincial Office, Davao Oriental Province. The study participants were 315 local government (LGU) employees in Davao Oriental out of a total of 3,062 employees. The sample size was determined by a quota of 65 samples per department, which Knofczynski and Mundfrom (2008) were able to give a good degree of prediction. Quota sampling is used here because the researcher chose to set the target number of LGU population required for this study. Quota sampling (Change of Mind, 2015) is one of three types of non-probability sampling; The other two methods are purposeful sampling and convenience sampling. With a quota of 65 employees per department, the sample population amounts to 315 local government employees, meaning each city has 20% of the population. The aim of the researchers was to provide a sufficient subsidy for the number of respondents. In this study, a staff member with at least one year of service experience and signed a consent form to participate in the study.

In addition, those excluded from this study are the private sector, those who are on leave, have withdrawn from the study, hold administrative positions or have less than one year of civil service experience, who have processed or had incomplete data and did not indicate their intention to participate in the study by a certificate of a consent form. Also, there is no requirement of justification if the participant wants to withdraw money early for any reason. Therefore, the researcher found that the staff of Davao Oriental and Mati City lacked teamwork, lacked empathy and support from the government, and assumed too many roles during the pandemic. bad behaviors at work that hinder the progress and development of the organization.

B. Materials and tools

There are three sets of questions approved by the authors of different studies, verified by the experts who developed the questionnaires. The revised standardized questionnaire is valuable in terms of content because it has undergone a series of modifications to classify the most valid and reliable questions. Moreover, it has been tested and proven by the authors themselves. The questionnaire was designed in a very comprehensive form with the help of expert reviewers to provide respondents with the ease and comfort needed to answer each question and understand the purpose of the study. . During the validation process, the questionnaire achieved an overall average score of 4.28, which is equivalent to the very descriptive score given by the validation experts.

In addition, pilot tests have also been applied. Cronbach alpha will be used to check the validity of the questionnaire with the following measures: public leadership, work commitment, and career commitment. Cronbach's alpha coherence is usually between 0 and 1. However, there is no lower limit for the coefficient. The closer the Cronbach's alpha is to 1, the greater the internal invariance of the variables in the scale (Gliem & Gliem,

2003) and modifications will be made to check the validity of the questionnaire.

The first part of the questionnaire focuses on the overt leadership of the supervisors and emphasizes accountability, legitimacy, ethics, and political loyalty; and network administration. with a Cronbach Alpha result of 0.912. The second questionnaire measures the level of professional commitment. with a Cronbach Alpha result of 0.877, which implies that the items have a relatively high consistency, have an Influential Career Commitment (APC), Continuous Career Commitment (CPC) and variable questionnaire subscales. The change of standard professional commitment is adjusted from (Meyer, Allen & Smith, 1993). The third part of the questionnaire is an employee scale of job commitment, which emphasizes strength, dedication and passion (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2003). Cronbach's alpha was applied to verify the reliability of the .818 tool.

The scales used to interpret Experienced Community Leadership, Work Commitment, and Professional Commitment are as follows.

Media Range Description Level Description:

- 4.20 – 5.00 Very High If this measure is still obvious to local government employees.
- 3.40-4.19 High If this measure is commonly observed among employees of local government.
- 2.60-3.39 Medium If this measure is sometimes followed among local government officials. 1.80-2.59 Low If this measure is rarely followed among local government agencies.
- 1.00-1.79 Very Low If this measure is never observed among local government employees.

The study used non-empirical quantitative research design method using correlation technique. The plan and structure of this study is to provide a reliable answer to a research question. Its purpose is to describe attainable characteristics such as achievements, attitudes, behaviors, and relationships. The non-empirical quantitative method is relevant to the present investigation because it addresses public leadership, work involvement, and expert involvement. Variables are not manipulated; they are only identified and studied when they occur in the natural environment (Educational Research, 2011).

Descriptive investigation is valuable in proving the facts that underlie scientific judgments. It provides essential knowledge about the nature of objects and people, and plays an important role in the development of tools that measure many things, tools that participate in all types of quantitative research as data collection tools. . The descriptive-correlation survey method is suitable for the current survey because it involves the description and identification of the independent and dependent variables (Creswell, 2013).

Mediation tests were used in this study as they probed the relationship between three variables such as public leadership, job engagement, and job engagement. Mediation analysis was used to explore and assess how an intermediate variable might influence variable X on variable Y (Cohen,

Cohen, West and Aiken, 2003). In addition, the intermediate variable (public leadership) is an intermediate variable between independent causal factors (work participation) and results (work participation). Its objective is to estimate the influence of variable Z (PSM) on the effect of X (OCB) on Y (OC) (Baron & Kenny, 1986). MacKinnon (2008) also explains that the intermediate variable blocks the direct association between variables X and Y, and thus sheds light on the nature of the link that variable X has on variable Y, but not that variable X has a relationship. Cause and Effect. directly on the variable Y. In other words, in the context of this study, public leadership (PI) redirects the direct link from work commitment to career commitment.

The first step in data collection was to obtain permission from the Rector of the Graduate School at the University of Mindanao, as well as the Governor and Mayor of Mati City, as well as various local government offices (town hall). (Davao Oriental Province) to allow researchers to conduct research. Once approved, the researcher went to different departments to personally deliver the approved letter with links from the Google form to the questionnaire. The researcher is grateful for the positive feedback from the offices of various departments in Davao Oriental.

Due to pandemic-related health requirements, the questionnaire was distributed online through the Google Form platform. Links to Google Forms were distributed to several groups through Facebook Messenger, and the School's Research Coordinator helped researchers distribute the Google link to local government offices. On the other hand, to ensure that there will be 315 responses, the survey has been open for at least a month. Data collection for the study began in the first week of August 2022 and ended in February 2022. To determine the significance of the mediating effect variable, Pearson-r was used. Furthermore, linear regression determines the predictors of the dependent variable given the list of independent variables. The study assesses whether people have leadership experience, job engagement, and career engagement.

On the other hand, the researcher adhered to comprehensive ethical standards in the study by following protocol reviews and standard criteria established by the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) with certification number 2022-013. Participants will have a voluntary will to contribute voluntarily without incurring any form of cost during the study. In addition, under the Data Protection Act 2012, the researcher ensures that the respondent's personal information is kept confidential. The researcher also ensures that the information gathered from the survey questions is accurate and that the sources of information are correctly recognized. Overall, before, during and after the study, the researcher complied with all ethical standards established by UMEREC.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The introduction, examination, and translation of the procured information are delineated in this portion of the paper based on the investigate targets of this think about. The stream of the introduction on the expressed theme is as takes

after: level of proficient learning communities; level of proficient commitment; level of work engagement; the critical relationship between proficient learning communities and work engagement; and proficient learning communities and teachers' adequacy; teachers' adequacy and work engagement; and the intercession examination.

A. Level of Open Administration Behavior

Appeared in Table 1 are the cruel scores for the markers of open authority behavior within the area of Davao Oriental. The in general cruel of the level of open administration behavior is 4.23 being portrayed as Exceptionally Tall expressive level with a standard deviation of 0.30. The marker of open authority behavior which is legality administration gotten a most elevated cruel of 4.38 which yielded a Really Tall graphic level. This can be favored by

organize governance leadership which gotten a cruel of 4.29 shown an Awfully Tall expressive level. Responsibility Authority features a cruel of 4.25 moreover portrayed as Exceptionally Tall graphic level. Moral administration has the least cruel of 4.11 which accomplished a Tall graphic level.

The exceptionally tall level of open administration behavior is united to the perspective of Manalo et al., (2020) fortified the discoveries which expressed that vision engages the chairman to expect and see the workforce as sensible and commendable individuals, and to have confidence afterward on state for each individual, attempting to offer assistance everybody in accomplishing that state. Fundamentally, vision enables faculty share an organization objective in which they expect with unimaginable want.

Table 1: Level of Public Leadership Behavior

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Accountability Leadership	0.32	4.25	Very High
Lawfulness Leadership	0.35	4.38	Very High
Conditional Knowledge	0.39	4.21	Very High
Ethical Leadership	0.42	4.11	High
Political Loyalty Leadership	0.46	4.13	High
Network Governance Leadership	0.36	4.29	Very High
Overall	0.30	4.23	Very High

The tall result of hope/faith is consistent to the build of Duran et al., (2021) who affirmed that when representatives have solid trust and confidence, they are deliberately willing to assist the mission of the school realized and emphatically seek after challenges with positive demeanor to attain organizational victory. The conclusive explanation of Decuyper and Schaufeli (2020) elucidated those representatives with higher trust tends to be more objective arranged, continue on to capture challenging objectives and able to protect the organization from any conceivable reactions in a more helpful way.

B. Level of Proficient Commitment

Reflected in Table 2 is the level of professional commitment of the neighborhood government representatives in Davao Oriental. As uncovered within the table, the generally level of proficient commitment was 4.12 with a standard deviation of 0.44. The standard deviation passed on that the respondents have an nearly homogeneous choice of answers from the given scale. This result portrayed a tall level of professional commitment among workers, which suggests that respondents frequently show commitment behaviors towards their organization. It might be gathered from the information that the pointer with the most elevated cruel rating of 4.18 or tall is- continuation proficient commitment. In differentiate, pointer with the most reduced cruel rating of 4.03v still tall is full of feeling proficient.

Table 2: Level of Professional Commitment

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Affective Professional Commitment	0.48	4.03	High
Continuance Professional Commitment	0.53	4.18	High
Normative Professional Commitment	0.53	4.16	High
Overall	0.44	4.12	High

commitment. The two highest indicators are continuance proficient commitment and with a cruel rating of 4.18 and standardizing proficient commitment with a cruel rating of 4.16 or tall.

The tall level of proficient commitment is due to the tall rating given by the respondents on the significance of full of feeling proficient commitment (APC), continuation proficient commitment (CPC), and standardizing proficient commitment, these markers enlisted an by and large tall rating which was the item of the tall scores evaluated by the

workers. This demonstrates a competent and committed representatives is one of the foremost vital components within the victory of any organizational framework.

The previous comes about suggest that the nearby government representatives in Davao Locale are not emphatically joined to their organization, which may be due to need of inspiration too. Arthi and Sumathi (2020) uncovered that those representatives who have solid enthusiastic connections to the organization are those who are likely to remain. Building a association between that

articulation and the result of this consider would conclude that the respondents don't have the inspiration that's anticipated from them. Fair as Sena (2020) and Margaretha et al., (2021) had long pronounced that representatives who needed passionate connection to their organization did not feel that they have a place to the organization, more so that they appeared less inclusion in their organization's exercises.

They too appeared less intrigued in seeking after the organization's objectives. Manalo et al, (2020) have found the reason behind why representatives appear less commitment to their organization. They pointed out that need of organizational bolster and less work fulfillment are the resultant impacts. While, Duran et al., (2021) underscored that less committed workers are those who are habitually missing from the work and who possible take off the

organization. Moreover, these less committed representatives appear lesser efficiency since they are not persuaded to do their obligations.

C. Level of Work Engagement

Information on level of work engagement of neighborhood government representatives in Davao oriental is reflected in Table 3 which was measured through a study survey with the taking after pointers: vigor, commitment and retention. It can be seen within the table that the in general cruel score was 3.95 or tall with a standard deviation of 0.48. The generally cruel score was depicted to be a tall level of work engagement which implies that respondents are oftentimes pulled in to take part in open benefit, representatives are locked in they are more included and work harder. They empower.

Table 3: Level of Work Engagement

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Feeling bursting with energy.	0.58	4.11	High
They are feeling like going to work.	0.60	4.13	High
Feeling strong and vigorous.	0.48	4.22	Very High
Being able to continue working for very long periods at a time.	0.34	3.95	High
Are being resilient workers.	0.66	4.15	High
Are being enthusiastic about their job.	0.61	3.79	High
Are being enthusiastic about their job.	0.56	3.79	High
Being proud of the work that they do.	0.46	4.13	High
Considering job as challenging.	0.64	4.09	High
Are being inspired with their job.	0.62	4.27	Very High
Working without wasting time.	0.59	3.81	High
When they are working, they forget everything else around them	0.54	3.73	High
Feeling happy when they are working intensely.	0.33	4.02	High
Being immersed in they work.	0.53	4.20	Very High
Are being attached to their work.	0.48	3.95	High

other workers around them to do their best, driving to higher worker engagement among the whole group. It can be gathered from the information that the thing with the most noteworthy cruel rating of 4.27 or tall is are being propelled with their work. In differentiate with the least thing when they are working, they disregard everything else around them with a cruel rating of 3.73. The whole cruel score was 3.95, which is considered to be very tall.

Information appears that a tall level of work engagement was oftentimes apparent, depicted as an imperative common viewpoint of a pioneer being showed all the time, which implies that the respondents are willing to put exertion into work and are indeed determined in confronting the issues. This result adjusts to the thought of Cohen et al. (2020) and Kimand Stop (2020) highlighted numerous focal points to representative engagement. Locked in representatives display tall vitality and solid mental flexibility, and they tend to intentionally contribute impressive effort in their allotted errands. In addition, profoundly locked in representatives tend to have a sense of their work's significance and challenges, and they express eagerness and pride in their work, hence upgrading their execution. apparent.

Within the same way, workers who are exceedingly locked in appear enthusiasm for their work and show a solid association to their organization. When the specialists are profoundly locked in, the level of client fulfillment too increments. Furthermore, with more profitable state of mind of specialists, the company would encounter the higher benefit, lower turnover, and lower mishap rate (Ismail et al., 2019).

➤ *Significance of the Relationship between the Public Leadership Behavior and Professional Commitment*

Outlined in Table 4 is the result of the test of relationship between open authority behavior and proficient commitment. The result appears that the by and large values uncover a positive and critical relationship between open administration behavior and proficient commitment. The in general result reflects that open administration behavior is emphatically related with proficient commitment since the by and large r-esteem is .816 with a p-value $p < 0.01$, thus dismissing the invalid speculation. Subsequently, there's a positive affiliation of the two factors.

In specific, it uncovered a positive and noteworthy relationship between all pointers of open administration behavior and proficient commitment, as uncovered within the P-value of less than 0.05, and with an r esteem of .692 on responsibility authority, .570 on legality authority, .422 on conditional information and .574 on moral administration. The terms, pioneer, in this study refers to somebody who starts alter within the gather, forms and endeavors to fulfill generally organizational targets.

The comes about appeared that open authority behavior and proficient commitment of representatives were emphatically related. Moreover, it was watched that the all pointers of open authority behavior with proficient

commitment was noteworthy. This result appears that thought open administration behavior is profitable for organization. These comes about bolster the hypothesis of Decuyper, and Schaufelim (2020) which states that administration behaviors influence the commitment. More particular authority behavior on representative execution. This implies that the way better the administration behavior will progress proficient commitment and empower the creation of a conducive working climate inside the organization. With the behavior of good administration would boost certainty that the higher not as it were within the organization / work unit is concerned, but too to other work units.

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Public Leadership Behavior and Professional Commitment

Public Leadership Behavior	Professional Commitment			Overall
	Affective Professional Commitment	Continuance Professional Commitment	Normative Commitment	
Accountability Leadership	.547* (0.000)	.613* (0.000)	.622* (0.000)	.692* (0.000)
Lawfulness Leadership	.471* (0.000)	.472* (0.000)	.526* (0.000)	.570* (0.000)
Conditional Knowledge	.522* (0.000)	.346* (0.000)	.239* (0.000)	.422* (0.000)
Ethical Leadership	.611* (0.000)	.629* (0.000)	.704* (0.000)	.754* (0.000)
Political Loyalty Leadership	.591* (0.000)	.643* (0.000)	.628* (0.000)	.722* (0.000)
Network Governance Leadership	.677* (0.000)	.569* (0.000)	.470* (0.000)	.662* (0.000)
Overall	.728* (0.000)	.698* (0.000)	.681* (0.000)	.816* (0.000)

➤ *Significance on the Relationship between Public Leadership Behavior and Work Engagement*

Depicted in Table 5 is the result of the test of relationship between open administration behavior is altogether related with their level of work engagement. This relationship was tried at 0.05 level of centrality. In specific, it uncovered a positive and critical relationship between all markers of open authority behavior and work engagement, as uncovered within the p-value of less than 0.05, and with an r esteem of .705. Going into information specifics uncovered that when pointers of open administration behavior were related with the pointers of work engagement it yielded the taking after comes about; responsibility authority is connected with the pointers of work engagement with the all of the R values where more noteworthy than $p < 0.05$ noteworthy level thus, noteworthy. To whole it up, open authority behavior and work engagement appear a positive direct relationship; this suggests that open administration behavior has something to do with work engagement.

The discoveries concur with the think about of Aggarwal et al., (2020) who said that when pioneers get it the columns of engagement, they can at that point start to use representative engagement for positive organizational results such as higher representative maintenance, more prominent client fulfillment, and made strides money related execution. There are endeavors pointing to extend the engagement of the workers by improving the authority.

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between the Public Leadership Behavior and Work Engagement

Public Leadership Behavior	Work Engagement Overall
Accountability Leadership	.619* (0.000)
Lawfulness Leadership	.541* (0.000)
Conditional Knowledge	.416* (0.000)
Ethical Leadership	.695* (0.000)
Political Loyalty Leadership	.632* (0.000)
Network Governance Leadership	.595* (0.000)
Overall	.745* (0.000)

➤ *Significance on the Relationship between Work Engagement and Professional Commitment*

Portrayed in Table 6 is the result of the test of relationship between work Engagement is altogether related with their level of proficient commitment. This relationship was tried at 0.05 level of centrality. In specific, it uncovered a positive and critical relationship between all pointers of work Engagement and proficient commitment., as uncovered within the p-value of less than 0.05, and with an r esteem of .890. When all pointers work Engagement is connected with the pointers of proficient commitment with the all of the R values where more noteworthy than $p < 0.05$ noteworthy level subsequently, critical. To whole it up, work Engagement and

proficient commitment. appear a positive direct relationship; this infers that work Engagement has something to do with proficient commitment.

The result concurs with the discoveries of Ahakwa et al., (2021) that representatives who are locked in in their work and committed to their organizations allow companies pivotal competitive advantages—including higher efficiency and lower employee turnover. In this way, it isn't astounding that organizations of all sizes and sorts have contributed significantly in approaches and hones that cultivate engagement and commitment in their workforces.

Table 6: Significance of the Relationship between the Work Engagement and Professional Commitment

Work Engagement	Professional Commitment			Overall
	Affective Professional Commitment	Continuance Professional Commitment	Normative Commitment	
Overall	.667* (0.000)	.779* (0.000)	.823* (0.000)	.890* (0.000)

➤ *On the Mediating Effect of Work Engagement*

Appeared in Table 7 is the relapse investigation on the intervening impact of work engagement onthe relationship between subleadership behavior and proficient commitment. The information in this table were utilized as input to the medgraph in Figure 1. As apparent within the consider of Noble and Kenny (1986), there are three stepsto be met for a third variable to be acting as go between, in Table 10 these are categorized as steps 1 to 3, step 4 is the ultimate step. In Step 1 (Way C) open administration behavior as free variable (IV) essentially predicts proficient commitment, the subordinate variable (DV). In Step 2 (Way A) work engagement (MV) altogether predicts proficient commitment, the arbiter (IV). In Step 3, open authority behavior, the go between (IV) essentially predicts proficient commitment. In Step 4 the combined impact of work engagement and open administration behavior on proficient commitment is noteworthy. In conclusion, the figure appears the results of the computation of the impact measure within the intercession test conducted between the three factors. The impact estimate measures how much between meta work

engagement and proficient commitment with $p < 0.01$ which implied halfway intervention and noteworthy since $p < 0.01$ which is less than .05. The application of the rule of Numerous Relapse is suitable since the information has passed the preparatory investigation by building up tall level of relationship of $p < 0.01$. Separated from the presumption of normality of information, a tall level of relationship among the factors could be a prerequisite to do absent with spurious show.

Table 7: Mediating Effect: Path Analysis

PATH	ESTIMATES		SE	C.R.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized			
PLB → WE	.691	.745	.036	19.290	***
WE → PC	1.000	.636	.054	18.583	***
PLB → PC	.499	.342	.050	9.989	***

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

As perceived by the local government employees in Davao Oriental, the level of open administration behavior is exceptionally tall and is additionally apparent in its pointers such as responsibility, legality, moral, political devotion; and organize administration administration. The level of proficient commitment is tall where its markers like full of feeling commitment, continuation commitment, and regulating commitment gotten tall evaluations. The level of work engagement is tall in vigor, commitment; and assimilation.

The think about concluded that open authority behavior of bosses and proficient commitment and essentially related. That's, the rise within the level of open authority behavior, gives rise moreover to the level of proficient commitment. In conclusion, the discoveries of this consider certified the suggestions which this consider was built upon. The discoveries asserted the recommendations of Ying and Zaman (2008) which states that authority behaviors influence the commitment. In this way, administration behavior will make strides proficient commitment and energize the creation of a conducive working climate inside the organization.

Aggarwal et al., (2021) that work engagement can emphatically impact employees' proficient commitment. In addition, the consider moreover confirmed the recommendations of Yiing and Zaman (2009) authority behavior is one of the imperative variables that influences organizational commitment. Within the same vein, the intervening impact of work engagement on the relationship between open authority behavior of supervisors and proficient commitment of representatives is critical. This shows that work engagement clarifies the fundamental connect between open administration behavior of administrators and proficient commitment of representatives.

The relationship test appeared a critical relationship between open authority behavior of bosses and proficient commitment. The relationship test appeared a noteworthy relationship between open administration behavior and work engagement. The relationship test appeared a noteworthy relationship between work engagement and proficient commitment.

The victory of work engagement can be related to different components. Other ponders may have proposed these as signs of work engagement in education. It is conceivable that other variables which manifest more broadly within the respondents were not among those included within

the ponder. Agreeing to Chaudhary & Singh (2017), within the think about concurs with the capacity to form a positive and vivacious impact on others by passing on considerations and information doubtlessly and effectively.

It involves orchestrating and organizing readily available approaches whereas utilizing relational skills to help in shaping engaging working connections with others. Hence, the information of work engagement. that's prevailing in a particular culture and environment would back organizers, chairmen, and experts to make procedures for thriving within the well-being administration of a multi-cultural workforce.

Based on the discoveries and conclusions specified over, the analyst proposes proposals for the open segment to proceed reinforcing the open administration and proficient commitment and work engagement by making and planning proficient improvement for government representatives. Encourage, within the light of work engagement there ought to be reliable introduction/ reorientation of the open school's code of morals, vision, and mission of to all modern and ancient government workers.

In spite of the fact that representatives were found to have an awfully tall level of open administration behavior but they were too found to as it were have tall levels of proficient commitment of workers and work engagement. in this manner, building upon these discoveries, the analyst prescribes that organization ought to back the organizational needs of workers so that their proficient commitment of workers and work engagement seem move forward.

The HR supervisors within the nearby government units may conduct needs appraisal (TNA) to address the proficient commitment of workers and work engagement concerns of the workers. a needs assessment is critical in impartially distinguishing wants of the workers since within the to begin with put it is the workers who precisely know what they need and what things to them the foremost. At that point, the result of this evaluation will direct HR Directors on what to do following taking after the comes about. Preparing or workshops advancing the proficient commitment of workers and work engagement characteristics may be conducted for these characteristics to reach their pinnacle (exceptionally tall), which is the anticipated level. Essentially, in spite of the fact that LGU representatives were found to have a tall vigor, ddcation and retention, still it is prescribed that LGUs or the city governments ought to moreover offer other alluring benefits to their workers. In conclusion, future analysts, to conduct more investigate with other government employees'

populaces, particularly open schools to authenticate the comes about of this ponder.

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ABOUT THE AUTHOR(S)

- Derbert B. General is a Senior Environmental Specialist. He is a candidate for the degree of Master of Arts in Public Administration at the University of Mindanao Davao City, Philippines.
- Dr. Lorna T. General is a Faculty under the program of educational management of the University of Mindanao Professional Schools of University of Mindanao Davao City, Philippines.

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